

Behaviour and Concentration of Trace and Rare Earth Elements in Basaltic Lava Flows of Indore Area, District Indore, (M.P.), India

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Abstract

The basic volcanic rocks around Indore (Longitude 75°50' to 76°0'E and Latitudes 22°35' to 22°50' N) belonging to Deccan Trap volcanic activity constitutes the central part of Malwa Plateau, which spread over an area of about 460 square kilometers and is mainly occupied by seven lava flows along with inter-trapeans and red bole/red clay bands. These basaltic rocks show a higher trace element concentration of vanadium and chromium with an average of 431.67 and 185.63 ppm respectively. These values of Vanadium are close to the values of Quartz-normative tholeiites and that of chromium is suggestive that it is camouflaged in pyroxene and fractionation in minerals led to iron enrichment. Concentration of Sr in the present rocks is agreeable with the tholeiitic basalt. Ba/Zr, Rb/Y, Nb/Y ratio of the rocks also attributed to low to moderate degree of partial melting of mantle whereas variation in the concentration of Zr and REE explain the crustal assimilation. On the basis of geochemical characteristics, it can be said that in the area of study the nature of magma is tholeiitic type it is also suggested that through fissures tholeiitic magma generated by partial melting at lower temperature has led to formation of lava flows of the study area.

1. Introduction

The Deccan traps occupy an area of about 5,12,000 sq. km. in Western and Central India (Krishnamurthy, P., 2020; Bhapkar et al., 2025). They are found as far as Belgaun in the south, Rajamundri in southeast. The Deccan traps attain maximum thickness near Bombay coast where they are estimated to be well above 7000 feet and thin out towards the east at Amarkantak and in Surguja where they are 500 feet thick, while near Belgaun south of Bombay they are 200 feet thick (Sharma et al., 2025).

The volcanic rocks show characteristics columnar jointing and vesicular zones at top of most of flows. Vesicles are filled with a variety of secondary minerals viz. zeolites, varieties of silica and calcite. The geochemical study of all the rocks are basaltic in nature.

2. Geology of the Area

The geological map of the study area has been prepared using Survey of India Toposheet Nos 46 N/13 and 46 N/14 (Fig. 1). Step like terraces and flats topped hills are very common in the region. At places mesa, butte and other feature are also seen (UNESCO World Heritage Centre, 2024). There are seven lava flows in the area under investigation have been delineated on the basis of flowing criterion:

1. The presence of Intertrappeans is a definite criterion for delineating two successive flows.
2. Presence of red bole/red clay band, but these zones are restricted in occurrence of individual flow top.
3. Palaeo - weathered zone at the top of the flow, but this also restricted and not continuously visible.
4. Vesicular zone at the top of the flow.
5. Geomorphic pattern specially the step like topography and the attitudinal confinement.

The flows are generally of pahoehoe type near to the source and become Aa or block lava type further away (Bagde et al., 2025). These types have been recognized in the area on the basis of characteristic features described by Mac Donald (1967) and Bagde et al., (2024).

Stratigraphic Succession of the studied area after (Verma, O., and Banerjee, D. M., 1992)

Group	Formation	Lithology / Characteristics
Malwa	Bargonda Formation	Massive basalt flows, compact, fine-grained
	Indore Formation	Vesicular/amygdaloidal basalt, red bole beds present
Group	Kankariya-Pirukheri Formation	Compact basalt with thin vesicular zones
	Kalisindh Formation	Compact basalt with occasional vesicles

Fig.1 Location map of the study area

3. Methodology

The field work for the present work was carried out in the study area. Reconnaissance survey of the study area was carried out in the first field session using Survey of India Toposheet No's. 46N/13 and 46N/14 on 1:50,000 scale.

The geological map of the area has been prepared using available satellite data (IRS ID LISS III) followed by extensive field work which includes mapping and demarcation of the exposed basaltic lava flow of the area along with their nature of contact, thickness of the flows, nature of the top and base of the individual flows etc.

Representative rock samples of the lava flows were taken from different levels flow wise- to understand geochemical characteristics.

Based upon the chemical analysis of 07 representative rock samples of the lava flows have been carried out for their major, trace and rare earth elements using ICMS at Geochemical Laboratory, NGRI, Hyderabad.

4. Results

4.1 Trace and REE ratios:

The concentration of various trace and rare earth elements is given in Table 1. Variations in Ba/Zr, Rb/Y and Nb/Y can be attributed to different degrees of partial melting of mantle. Variation in Zr, rare earth elements and Rb/Nb indicate fractional crystallization and significant coupled crustal assimilation away from the Deccan plume center. These ratios have been calculated for the basaltic lava flows of the study area and mentioned in the Table 2. The average values of trace elements concentration in the study are given in figure 2. Nb/Y ratios ranges from 0.19-1.37 with an average value of 0.28; Rb/Y ratios ranges from 0.095-0.82 with an average value of 0.26 and Ba/Zr ratios ranges from 0.24-0.49 with an average value of 0.31. This may be suggested that variation in Ba/Zr, Rb/Y and Nb/Y ratios of the basaltic lava flow of the area may be explained by low to moderate degree of partial melting of mantle, while the crustal assimilation can be explained by the variation of Zr and REE. Chatterjee and Bhattacharjee (2008) have pointed out, that the greater crustal assimilation in the Narmada – Tapti rift region may be related to longer and greater magma-wall rock interaction in shallow crustal magma chambers due to crustal extension-related enlargement of the magma chambers, recharge with fresh, hot magma and convective mixing (Duraishwami et al. 2020).

Table-1**Trace and Rare-Earth Elements abundance in the Basaltic Lava Flows of the study area (in ppm)**

Element	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅	F ₆	F ₇	Range	Average
Sc	44.92	52.10	50.80	49.62	17.29	56.13	50.45	17.29 -56.13	45.90
V	413.60	540.77	534.44	441.59	126.56	345.32	569.47	126.56-569.47	431.67
Cr	96.52	131.44	126.05	597.77	67.43	147.96	132.29	67.43 - 597.77	185.63
Co	61.67	70.86	73.17	73.93	19.90	55.42	74.08	19.90 - 74.08	61.29
Ni	97.18	115.35	118.06	253.68	39.12	95.71	107.01	39.12 - 253.68	118.01
Cu	225.63	309.17	343.13	238.28	74.75	247.88	356.33	74.75 - 356.33	256.45
Zn	234.97	188.05	178.13	149.49	93.09	155.97	258.49	93.09 - 258.04	179.74
Ga	28.84	28.23	27.86	24.28	8.51	24.40	30.24	8.51 - 30.24	24.62
Rb	40.40	16.70	13.40	2.13	0.99	4.78	12.36	0.99 -40.40	12.96
Sr	347.96	295.42	291.74	249.65	105.39	197.67	343.63	105.39-347.96	261.63
Zr	298.60	253.26	243.94	156.66	59.49	174.17	256.90	59.49 - 258.60	200.43
Nb	15.19	17.98	17.13	9.09	3.50	9.85	18.87	3.50 - 18.87	13.08
Cs	1.03	0.29	0.24	0.08	0.06	0.09	0.23	0.06 - 1.03	0.28
Ba	93.87	67.24	59.68	45.45	18.97	85.84	74.52	18.97 - 93.87	63.93
Hf	6.17	6.19	5.85	3.82	1.42	4.25	6.19	1.42 - 6.19	4.84
Ta	1.05	0.93	1.35	0.70	0.34	0.75	1.40	0.34 - 1.43	0.93
Pb	2.64	2.25	2.74	2.59	1.60	2.30	1.93	1.60 - 2.74	2.29
Th	4.13	2.77	2.47	1.11	0.88	4.03	1.76	0.88 - 4.13	2.45
U	0.47	0.46	0.44	0.17	0.08	0.42	0.29	0.08 - 4.47	0.33
Y	49.14	52.12	50.38	36.39	17.70	50.26	54.23	17.70 - 54.23	44.30
La	28.47	21.25	20.53	10.65	5.25	19.95	19.63	5.25 - 28.47	17.96
Ce	58.66	47.18	45.46	25.23	11.86	38.70	44.16	11.86 - 58.66	38.75
Pr	6.82	5.88	5.62	3.37	1.61	4.42	5.83	1.61 - 6-82	4.79
Nd	34.85	31.72	30.34	19.01	9.33	21.94	32.05	9.33 - 34.85	25.60
Sm	8.14	7.88	7.66	5.31	2.59	5.35	8.34	2.59 - 8.34	6.46
Eu	2.52	2.54	2.41	1.81	0.85	1.73	2.73	0.85 - 273	2.08
Gd	8.57	8.55	8.11	5.65	2.81	6.43	9.02	2.81 - 9.02	7.02
Tb	1.23	1.27	1.25	0.89	0.44	1.06	1.37	0.44 - 1.37	1.07
Dy	8.17	8.62	8.35	6.06	2.94	7.50	8.91	2.94 - 8.91	7.22
Ho	1.58	1.69	1.63	1.21	0.57	1.59	1.75	0.57 - 1.75	1.43
Er	4.10	4.34	4.13	3.00	1.44	4.39	4.51	1.44 - 4.51	3.70
Tm	0.46	0.49	0.45	0.34	0.17	0.51	0.50	0.17 - .50	0.41
Yb	2.54	2.73	2.67	1.90	0.98	3.03	2.86	0.98 - 3.03	2.38
Lu	0.57	0.60	0.59	0.42	0.20	0.67	0.62	0.20 - .67	0.52

F1 (Flow 1) to F7 (Flow 7) are Basaltic Lava Flows of the study area.

Table 2
Significant ratios of Trace and Rare Earth Elements of the study area

Ratio	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅	F ₆	F ₇	Range	Average
Nb/Y	0.30	0.34	0.34	0.24	0.19	0.19	0.34	0.19-0.37	0.28
Rb/Y	0.82	0.32	0.26	0.028	0.055	0.095	0.22	0.095-0.82	0.26
Ba/Zr	0.31	0.26	0.24	0.29	0.31	0.49	0.29	0.24-0.49	0.31

Fig.2 Average values of trace elements concentration in the study area.

5. Conclusions

The basaltic lava flows of the Indore area, forming part of the Malwa Group of the Deccan Traps, represent a well-defined sequence of seven flows interbedded with red bole horizons and Intertrappeans sediments, indicating episodic volcanic activity with intervening periods of quiescence. The geomorphology of the region, characterized by step-like topography, mesas, and buttes, is typical of basaltic terrains.

Geochemically, the lava flows are tholeiitic in nature, as evidenced by their trace element composition. The relatively high concentrations of vanadium (average ~431.67 ppm) and chromium (average ~185.63 ppm) indicate a mantle-derived magma, with chromium largely

hosted in pyroxene phases and vanadium values comparable to quartz-normative tholeiites. The concentration of strontium further supports this tholeiitic affinity.

Trace element ratios such as Nb/Y, Rb/Y, and Ba/Zr suggest that the magma was generated by a low to moderate degree of partial melting of the mantle. Variations in Zr and rare earth elements (REE) indicate that the magma underwent fractional crystallization along with significant crustal assimilation, likely due to prolonged interaction between magma and surrounding crustal rocks in shallow magma chambers.

Overall, the study indicates that the basaltic lava flows of the Indore area were emplaced through fissure eruptions of tholeiitic magma, generated at relatively low degrees of partial melting and subsequently modified by fractional crystallization and crustal assimilation processes, resulting in the observed geochemical characteristics.

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